

IMPACT OF EMPLOYEE MOTIVATION ON ORGANIZATIONAL PRODUCTIVITY

(A CASE STUDY OF GLORIOUS VISION UNIVERSITY)

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ABSTRACT

This study was purposely conducted to analyze the outcome that motivation has on the performance of workers in an organization using Glorious Vision University as a case study. Motivation comes in handy for a firm that wishes to attain its goals and prospects. The broad objective of this research is to analyze the impact of motivation on the performance of staffs in Glorious Vision University. The specific objectives are to: Investigate, the extent to which goals impact the performance of employees in Glorious Vision University. Analyze the impact of monetary factors on the employee performance. Explore the extent to which recognition and reward programs impact the employee performance. When the workers are motivated, they improve their commitment to the firm's objectives and so it is the duty of every firm to incorporate the various motivating factors in their system. This study was based on the analysis of the impact of goals, monetary incentives and recognition and rewards on the worker's performance. A descriptive research style and a sample of 130 employees from the various colleges were used. Questionnaires were used to collect data which was then analyzed and presented on tables. The study found out that goals were widely used as motivators in the organization's performance. It also found out that the employees were dissatisfied with the salaries they were getting which results to ineffective organizational performance. The recognition and reward systems were also inequitable. The study concluded that the employees in Glorious Vision University were not well motivated and recommendations to increase the motivation were given.

Keyword: Goals; Monetary Factors; Finance; Incentives; Motivation and Productivity.

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INTRODUCTION

The term motivation means to move and it came from a Latin word 'movers'. According to Lang, (2010), motivation is offering persons' enticements that make them behave in a certain anticipated way. Motivation comes in two ways which are extrinsic and intrinsic. External motivation is the conduct done not for its own sake but the outcomes accompanying it. These consequences comprise salaries, profits, and working environment. External pleasantries are from the firm as money and elevations from managers and colleagues by acknowledgement (Pinder, 2014). Intrinsic motivation is that behavior produced by a person as a result of the pleasing experiences linked with the conduct itself (Akanbi, 2011). These experiences come from the motivation that is distinctive of the occupation itself (Brown, 2003). Examples of intrinsic motivation are getting a positive acknowledgment, gratefulness, a sense of accomplishment and accomplishing the test.

Motivating the staff is one of the strategies the management employ to increase effectual job administration amongst the workers in the organization (Cherian & Jacob, 2013). An employee's capability partly determines his output. The other determining factor is his motivational level. The human resource manager is responsible for making sure that there is job commitment at the workplace and this can only be achieved through motivation. Generally, individuals are motivated in circumstances where they can take part, they feel achievement and obtain recognition for their efforts, where the communication is regular and prospects for career and know-how development (Guion, 1998). Motivation is vital for better performance and it is therefore important to recognize what motivates the workers for better performance.

Brown et al. (1998) documented that motivation is concerned with why employees do what they do. This helps in answering the question of why employees go to work and perform a good job. The manager is primarily tasked with providing the employees with and maintains a surrounding in which the employees can perform their duties efficiently and realize the goals of the organizations (London & Bray, 1984). Employees have different abilities as well as what motivates them Carson *et al.* (1997).

Demirel *et al* (2013) This paper aimed at studying the impact of motivation on workers' productivity where the case study Glorious Vision University will be used (Saraih& Sultan,2018). Businesses are in existence to give services to the public. To meet this objective, individuals are employed by firms. These people need to be productive and to do this, they must be motivated. Motivating employees means meeting their needs so that they may have the motive to work. Employees tend to leave work due to lack of motivation and this becomes costly for the firm as recruitment is a tedious activity. To help limit these costs, this study was carried out to determine how motivation affects employee productivity. .

Statement of Problem

As at 2019 to 2022, workers (teaching and non-teaching staffs) in Glorious Vision university resigns from their work and this are works that got them motivated when they applied to the extent of getting their job acceptance letters. The researcher is looking into the various factors that causes or factors that are likely to motivate their resignation. Workers leave organization due to the fact that they are not motivated enough. Some are not willing to leave because they are enjoying some benefit in terms of promotion, which leads to increase in salaries and wages, bonus and some other incentives. The workers of Glorious Vision University will prefer financial incentives to non-financial incentives, more especially the junior workers ,due to the fact that such incentives are not used as a motivational technique, the institution have the problem and challenges of retention of their employees. Hence low performance and productivity becomes the end result and finally work dissatisfaction.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Goals

Lunenburg, (2011) define a goal as the intention of a deed or duty that an individual determinedly wishes to attain or accomplish. This motivational strategy is employed by many firms as a way of pointing individual's hard work at work and offering an average against which productivity can be measured (Lunenberg, 2011;Sultan & Noor, 2017). Goal setting is a cognitive theory of motivation founded on the principle that individuals possess wants that can be believed to be particular results they wish to accomplish. Mone et al (2011) describe goal

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setting theory has led to the advancement of an enormous body of experimental study on motivation at the workplace and it has become a very dominating paradigm in today's literature. Helms (2006) Goal has been the underlying explanation for all major theories of work. Motivation has also acknowledged goal setting as one of the most successful methods of transforming conduct in the workplace. Carson et al. (1997)

Financial incentives

Herzberg *et al.*, (1957) see money is a key incentive as its influential value is very high. Workers will always need to be remunerated for the effort they put in. Adequate incentives motivate staffs by making them have the right attitude towards work which heightens the productivity in the organization.

monetary incentive, affect employees' commitment. When the monetary incentives surpass the costs of leaving a firm, employees tend to be motivated to remain in the firm (Harunavamwe, & Kanengoni, 2013). Money is a very suitable motivator since people fear losing their jobs for the fear of being unable to survive in the economy. The main goal of every organization is to meet its corporate objectives which are facilitated by hiring competent employees. These employees are obtained only if the working conditions are good, the job security is assured and the salaries are competitive.

Recognition and Rewards

Hong et al (1995) an organization's ways of rewarding and recognizing its employees contributes to the level of motivation the employees get. The motivation that the workers possess determines how productive they will be. When utilized appropriately, rewards can motivate workers to perform better which translates into the success of the organization (Hafiza et al., 2011). A job that offers chances for recognition and rewards tends to motivate the workers making them very productive. Employees are positively reinforced when they are rewarded with tangible tokens as rewards for good work done. Rewards often have a positive influence on the productivity of employees and an appreciation from the immediate boss usually motivates the workers massively. Rewards ought to be carefully thought of since they may end up being a loss for the organization (Sultan et al., 2018).

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Recognition and rewards are very good ways to keep the employees motivated and this makes them more focused at achieving the company goals (Salancik, 1977). Güngör (2011) document explains that appreciating a worker makes him or her to have a high self-regard and this makes them be confident about making contributions to the firm's objectives.

Theories of Motivation

The three major theories used in this study motivational theories that have come to us from authors such as

Fredrick Taylor, Abraham Maslow: The Need Theory: The Two Factors Theory: (Herzberg) Theory, as well as the classical theory of motivation.

1. **Frederick Taylor:** known as “The father of scientific management” who is inseparably tied with the classical theory was of the view that men could produce more if only they earn more. His plan was unique in that it greatly increased the reward for high productivity. Thus, men were able to double their wages under the system. It is clear that the classical theory makes the assumption that money is the best motivation. The power of money as a motivator has never been generally established with total agreement. People exist who can be motivated by money just as those who have none beyond being motivated by money. Tailors classical theory fails to specify other important considerations that affect individual motivation to work, by trying to make money the simple solution.

2. **The Need Theory: Abraham Maslow:**

Most people never reach the point where they no longer want more money. But there definitely comes a time when we begin to think that there is more to derive out of life than mere pay packets. Abraham Maslow (1970) has constructed a continuum of the human needs that motivate. This is popularly known as the Need hierarchy. These needs are:

- (a) **Physical Needs:** These needs are associated with man's strong drive towards self-preservation. They include shelter, food and water.
- (b) **Security Needs:** The two types of security needs are physical and economic. In as much as physical security is important, people however lay greater emphasis on economic security. They want to be secure against loss of income, unemployment and lack of income in one's old age.

- (c) Social Needs: people need to feel relevant and accepted in any group they are identified with. They also need to have some influence over other group members.
- (d) Esteem Needs: These are highlighted in the fact that man needs recognition in whatever he does, status and prestige.
- (e) Self-Actualization Needs: This is the need to do what one is best suited for. Some people aspire to be politicians, leaders and dictators and are consequently power-hungry. Such people believe they are best suited for these, in terms of their skill and ability. Such factors as higher responsibility/advancement, challenging work, growth opportunity etc is all included here. It may be convenient at this point, to combine physiological and security needs into lower or “economic” needs.

3. *The Two Factors Theory: (Herzberg)*

Herzberg conducted experiments on motivation, and drawing from the data collected, he identified two vital factor in every job. First, there are certain elements in a job that he, called “maintenance factors” or hygiene factors, which include adequate salary, adequate working conditions, job security and fringe benefits. From Herzber’s point of view, these things are necessary for the worker to even begin to be motivated. The “maintenance factors” are those which when not present, will cause dissatisfaction, and if present will prevent dissatisfaction, but will not motivate people to greater performance. Herzberg (1964, p.3-7) has named these maintenance factors, the “Hygiene” factors in a poor analogy I must say with the way the term is used in preventive medicine.

He concluded that there were ten maintenance factors, namely: Company policy and administration, Technical supervision, Salary, Interpersonal relations with supervisor, Interpersonal relation with peers, Interpersonal relations with subordinates, Job security, Personal life, Working conditions and Status. Beyond the maintenance factors Herzberg calls the remaining ones the motivational factors. These are the things that could really bring about positive attitudes and motivation. However, if these are lacking positive attitude and motivation will not emerge. The motivational factors, which he called ‘satisfiers’ includes: Recognition, Achievement, Advancement, The work itself, the possibility of growth, and Responsibility

The insight into the motivational process that was gained via Herzberg's research blends very well with Maslow's theory. For instance, Herzberg's maintenance factors are roughly-equivalent to Maslow's lower (economic). Needs – the things a worker must have to begin with. Herzberg's motivational factors correspond with Maslow's higher level needs. The significance of the two factor theory lies in the recognition that those organizations or individual managers who have traditionally approached the subject of motivation from a purely maintenance (or hygiene) perspective, have been seriously deluding themselves in some ways, because all they have succeeded in doing in most cases is preventing dissatisfaction. No positive motivation has this resulted beyond the neutral level. Furthermore, managers are often limited in their control over wages- one of the most important elements of the hygiene (maintenance) factors. Therefore, not only the effectiveness of money as a motivator in question, but also the extent to which any individual manager has control over it. Managers cannot motivate people with incentives over which they have no control (Uzoma 1989)

Empirical Review

A lot has been written about this topic motivation by different researchers. It is mostly researchers that discuss object areas in both the business organization and it is important to note that success and failure of any business organization depends on the performance of its manpower. An organization is a socio-economic system which combines technology and humanity when an organization is formed. It normally requires man, money, machine and materials to pursue the achievement of its goal and objectives. Among these resources the human resources is the greatest asset in the enterprise. People make decision concerning all other organizational resources and come up with an idea to put them into operation. Therefore staffs are the life-blood and success of the organization ultimately depends on them. The individual staff therefore required planned development or training to improve their level and areas of operation of the organizations objectives must be effectively achieved. This is because the human elements on their parts need to be effective to an extent so as to know what to do and how to do it given the enabling environment. This means that the individuals that makeup the organization staff must be knowledgeable and skilled in their areas of acclaimed profession. This depends upon the extent of impact such expertise would make on the achievement of the organization. Some writers have turned their attention to the nature of human behaviour in *A Publication of School of Postgraduate Studies, Glorious Vision University, Ogwa, Edo State*

relation to the management function of Macgregor (1967:349) and other is the need to recognize and understand human behaviour and motivation. A motivated worker will work very well not minding what it takes, and the stress one undergoes but toward high profit. Profit is one of the main objectives, the manager must as a matter of fact, find what will spur the employers under him to high performance, furthermore, motivated employee might reduce the problem of high labour turn over.

Productivity is an important term to individuals, groups, organizations and nations. Despite its importance, there is lack of universal definition of productivity. Comparative analysis of productivity is sometimes difficult for example. Comparing productivity of a work using manual system of operation with another using automatic system of operation may be difficult. However Bedeian (1987) has defined productivity as the unit of output produced divided by the number of units of resources applied. A productivity organization will produce more units of outputs with given units of input.

Research Methodology

This study used a descriptive design where questionnaires were administered to the employees. Based on the literature reviewed, questionnaires were established to help in collecting the primary data for this study. The questionnaires were handed over to the target employees who filled them up and returned them to researcher. Using charts and graphs the data was analyzed to determine the effect of the motivational factors on the employees' performance (Liu, Siu, & Shi, 2010).

Population and Sampling Technique

The target population for this study comprised of employees from Glorious Vision University, which comprises a total of 195. A total of 130 respondents were selected using the taro Yamane sampling technique method. They were given the questionnaires and upon filling them, they presented them back to the researcher. The primary data that was obtained from the questionnaires was analyzed to determine how motivation affects the employees' performance.

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Data Collection Instruments

The management was contacted through a letter of request to permit the researcher to carry out the study in the institution. Self-administered questionnaires were used to obtain primary data (Hanson *et al.*, 2002). The reason for choosing these questionnaires was that they offered convenience to the respondent and there was no need of setting up interview appointments which at times are time consuming (Phellas *et al.*, 2011). The questionnaires were also useful in that they eliminated the bias that could be brought about by the interviewer in case of interviews. Questionnaires are also inexpensive thus economical especially when conducting a research on a large sample. The questionnaires were tested on a few employees before being given to the whole target population. The respondents were issued a letter which guaranteed them of anonymity attached to the questionnaire. The data that was collected was purely for academic purposes and the respondents were clearly informed about this. An informed consent was obtained from all the respondents to make sure all of them participated out of personal will. Privacy and confidentiality of any information obtained was maintained throughout the study.

Methods of Data Analysis

Data obtained from the questionnaires was both qualitative and quantitative. Tables were used to analyze it with the help of descriptive statistics. Correlation assessments were carried out to give interpretations about the respondents from the sample.

Results and Findings

130 questionnaires were given to the population and only 128 were returned and so the results were based on 128 questionnaires.

GENDER

The questionnaires required an indication of a person's gender and out of the 128 respondents, 70 were male which translated into 55% while 58 were female representing 45% of the total respondents as shown in table 2. This shows there are more male employees than female employees in Glorious Vision University.

GENDER

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
MALE	70	53.8	53.8	53.8
FEMALE	60	46.2	46.2	100.0
Valid Total	130	100.0	100.0	

Source: field work 2023

The table above shows the gender of the respondents.

The table indicates that 55% of the employees interviewed were male while 45% of the employees were female. This showed some predominance of the male gender in GVU.

Age group

The questionnaires asked about the age of the respondents where they were to tick according to their range

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Below 25	31	23.8	23.8	23.8
26-30 years	47	36.2	36.2	60.0
31-35 years	36	27.7	27.7	87.7
36-40 years	16	12.3	12.3	100.0
Valid Total	130	100.0	100.0	

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Source: field work 2023

Table 3: age of the respondents

The table 3 above shows the age of the respondents

The results show that 23.85% of the respondents were below 25 years, 36.15% were between 26-30 years, 27.69 % were aged between 31 and 35 and 12.31% were aged between 36 and 40. This indicated that most of the employees in Glorious Vision University were aged between 31 and 35 years.

Impact of goals as a motivational tool

The respondents were to indicate some aspects on goals as a motivator stating whether they strongly agree, agree, neutral disagree or strongly disagree. The outcomes were as shown:

Participation in coming up with the goals

The participants were to specify whether they are permitted to contribute and be part of setting the goals. The results were as shown below Participation in goal development

SCALE

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	
Valid	Strongly disagree	17	13.1	13.1	13.1
	Disagree	21	16.2	16.2	29.2
	Neutral	27	20.8	20.8	50.0
	Agree	55	42.3	42.3	92.3
	Strongly agree	10	7.7	7.7	100.0
	Total	130	100.0	100.0	

Source: field work 2023

Significance of the goals

The participants were asked about how significant they thought their goals were to the organizations’ objectives. The results were as shown below:

SIGNIFICANCE

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Very significant	78	60.0	60.0	60.0
Valid Merely significant	39	30.0	30.0	90.0
Invalid Insignificant	13	10.0	10.0	100.0
Total	130	100.0	100.0	

Source: field work 2023

Table 4.5 Significance

Table 4.5 shows the significance of the goals

The table shows that 10% of the respondents thought that their goals were insignificant, 30% of the respondents thought that their goals were merely insignificant while 60 % thought that their goals were very significant. This meant that most of the respondents understood the significance of their goals to the organization.

Hypothesis testing 1

Ho: goals have no significant impact on employee’s performance

H1: Goals have a significant impact on employee’s performance

The table in **fig4.5** shows that 42.31% agreed, 20.77% were neutral, 16.15% disagreed, 13.08% strongly disagreed while 7.69% strongly agreed. This was an indication that most employees were allowed to participate in setting the goals they were expected to achieve.

And therefore we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis. This proves that Goals have a significant impact on employee’s performance.

Effect of monetary incentives on the performance

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The participants were required to respond on how satisfied they were with their pay and they answered as shown below:

SATISFACTION

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Satisfied	11	8.5	8.5	8.5
Dissatisfied	105	80.8	80.8	89.2
Valid Unsure	14	10.8	10.8	100.0
Total	130	100.0	100.0	

Source: field work 2023.

Table 4.6 satisfaction with pay

Satisfaction with pay

8.462% of the respondents were satisfied with their pay, 80.77% were dissatisfied with their salary and 10.77% were unsure of their satisfaction with their pay. This showed that most of the workers were dissatisfied with their salary.

Hypothesis testing II

Ho: monetary incentives do not significantly influence employee’s job satisfaction

H2: monetary incentives significantly influence employee’s job satisfaction

The table in **fig4.6** shows that 8.462% of the respondents were satisfied with their pay, 80.77% were dissatisfied with their salary and 10.77% were unsure of their satisfaction with their pay. This showed that most of the workers were dissatisfied with their salary.

This was an indication that most employees were not satisfied with their salaries. And therefore we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis. This proves that Goals have a significant impact on employee’s performance.

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Recognition and rewards

The participants were asked about the level of recognition and rewards in the organization and the results were as follows.

ADEQUACY

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Adequate	91	70.0	70.0	70.0
Inadequate	39	30.0	30.0	100.0
Valid Total	130	100.0	100.0	

Source: field work 2023

Table 4.7 recognition and rewards

30 % of the participants felt that recognition and rewards in the organization were inadequate while 70% felt that the recognition and rewards were adequate.

Hypothesis testing III

Ho: There is no significant relationship, between rewards and employee’s job performance.

H3: There is a significant relationship between rewards and employee’s job performance.

The table in **fig4.7** shows that 30 % of the participants felt that recognition and rewards in the organization were inadequate while 70% felt that the rewards were adequate.

This showed that most of the workers were dissatisfied with the inadequate recognition and reward.

Conclusion and Summary of findings

Based on the research findings, it is concluded that the administration at glorious vision university lets the workers take part in setting their goals and that they also had an understanding

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of the significance of the goals on the overall goals and objectives of the institution . The research came to the conclusion that staffs in glorious vision university were dissatisfied with the salaries they were getting, and this de-motivated them, thus affecting their performance.

The results of the study led to the conclusion that the recognition and reward systems being utilized in Glorious Vision University were inadequate and thus they did not motivate the employees enough to improve their performance.

The following recommendations are hereby made:

Depending on the findings that Glorious Vision University did not satisfy the economic requirements of the workers through salaries. This research would therefore recommend a re-evaluation of the salaries because workers relate finances to the worth placed over them by the firm. A higher salary will mean they feel more worthy thus improving their performance.

Since the recognition and reward systems in Glorious Vision University is inadequate as of now, this study would recommend that the Glorious Vision University consult with the workers on the best way to make the existing systems more equitable for all so that the motivation of the workers may increase leading to improved performance.

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